

A Method for the Determination of Titanium as Phosphate.

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For the determination of small quantities of titanium, the colorimetric method is very satisfactory, except when vanadium, chromium or alkali salts are present. The Gooch method (*Chem. News*, 1885, 52, 55, 68) depends upon adding alkali acetate and carrying out a basic acetate precipitation. The Baskerville method (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1894, 16, 427, 475; Gooch, *Proc. Amer. Acad. Arts Sci.*, 1885, 12, 435; Chatard, *Amer. Chem. J.*, 1891, 13, 106) is based upon the fact that a nearly neutral solution of iron and titanium chlorides when boiled with sulphurous acid at moderate dilution gives a precipitate of titanium hydroxide, while the iron remains in solution in the ferrous state. Thornton (*Amer. J. Sci.*, 1914, iv, 37, 173, 407) recommends the use of cupferron. The Chancel-Stromayer method consists of precipitating titanium with sodium thiosulphate added to the pyrosulphate melt. The method of Barneby and Isham (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 32, 957) consists of fusion with sodium carbonate and a little potassium nitrate, extraction with hot water, solution of the ferric oxide and sodium titanate in HCl, extraction of the ferric chloride with ether, reduction of the slight traces of iron with sulphurous acid, precipitation of the titanate by boiling in acetic acid solution, filtration and ignition of the precipitate to titanium dioxide.

In presence of phosphoric acid, the precipitation of *meta*-titanic acid is hindered due to hydrolysis; so there is always a risk of precipitating it in the presence of any soluble phosphates. But if the titanium is precipitated wholly as a phosphate, it can be determined quantitatively. The method as worked out by the author is given below.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Any ore of titanium or titanium-bearing clay *viz.*, bauxite, is first powdered very finely and passed through a 90-mesh sieve. The sample is then dried at 110°. The dried sample is taken for analysis. From 0.5 to 1.0 g. of the sample is first fused in a platinum

crucible with sodium carbonate for at least half an hour (some ores require a preliminary treatment with HF and H₂SO₄, prior to fusion). This converts the titanium into sodium titanate. The melt is now leached with 200 c.c. of boiling water, filtered and washed thoroughly with hot water. Alumina and silica go into solution both as soluble sodium salts. The filtrate is rejected; titanium remains in the residue as sodium titanate, Na₂TiO₃. (This sodium titanate undergoes hydrolysis and an acid titanate of sodium, 2Na₂O · 9TiO₂ · 5H₂O is precipitated. Though sodium titanate is hydrolysed in water, none of it goes into solution. This is soluble, in both sulphuric and hydrochloric acids. But the HCl solution when boiled long is again hydrolysed and *meta*-titanic acid is precipitated). About 30 c.c. of dilute H₂SO₄ (1:5) is added to the residue and gently boiled to dissolve. The solution is then cooled a little, diluted to 200 c.c. with cold water, nearly neutralised with ammonium hydroxide and 20 c.c. of 20 p.c. solution of ammonium phosphate are added. Then the solution is further diluted with hot water to about 400 c.c. If a precipitate forms at this stage, it is just dissolved with dilute H₂SO₄ and an excess of 5 c.c. acid is further added. The amount of free H₂SO₄ in the solution should not exceed 2 per cent. Now 10 g. of sodium thiosulphate and 15 c.c. of pure acetic acid are added (this will reduce all the iron in the ferric state to the ferrous state) and the solution boiled for about half an hour. Now all the titanium will be precipitated as phosphate, leaving iron in solution. (When solutions containing iron entirely in the ferrous state are treated with an alkali phosphate in presence of excess of Na₂S₂O₃, no iron is precipitated). The solution is now filtered and the residue is washed well with hot water, ignited and weighed as Ti₂P₂O₉.

The reactions are as follows:—

Titanium forms a basic phosphate with acid or a soluble phosphate.

In presence of sulphuric acid it will give

This residue when ignited leaves a pyrophosphate of the composition, 2TiO₂ · P₂O₅ or Ti₂P₂O₉.

Some experimental data are given below. Pure TiO_2 of known composition was taken for analysis.

TABLE I.

Wt. of phosphate.	Wt. of TiO_2 from phosphate.	Wt. of TiO_2 detmd. as oxide.	Actual wt. of TiO_2 taken.
0.2760 g.	0.1463 g.	0.1442 g.	0.1450 g.
0.2270	0.1203	0.1206	0.1210
0.2830	0.1500	0.1520	0.1520
0.1770	0.0938	0.0948	0.0945
0.1764	0.0935	0.0944	0.0945

All the above results were obtained by using H_2SO_4 as the solvent for the leached residue.

By using dilute hydrochloric acid as the solvent, the following results were obtained.

TABLE II.

Wt. of phosphate.	Wt. of TiO_2 from phosphate.	Wt. of TiO_2 detmd. as oxide.	Actual wt. of TiO_2 taken.
0.1710 g.	0.0906 g.	0.0930 g.	0.0910 g.
0.2951	0.1564	0.1580	0.1565

From the above figures it is evident that it does not matter much if H_2SO_4 or HCl is used as the solvent for the leached residue.

In the case of natural ores the following figures were obtained.

TABLE III.

Wt. of phosphate-precipitate.	Wt. of TiO_2 from phosphate.	TiO_2 determined by Oxide-method.
A. 0.3755 g.	0.1990 g.	0.1983 g.
0.3752	0.1988	0.1984
B. 0.3775	0.2001	0.2000
0.3779	0.2003	0.2001
C. 0.1899	0.1006	0.1006
0.1900	0.1007	0.1006

The sample 'A' contained 54.38 p.c. iron; sample 'B' contained 40.44 p.c. iron and sample 'C' contained 56.80 p.c. iron.

Analysis of samples of Ilmenite.—0.5 G. of the sample was taken for analysis.

TABLE IV.

Wt. of phosphate-precipitate.	Wt. of TiO ₂ from phosphate.	TiO ₂ determined by Oxide-method.
0.4566 g.	0.2420 g.	0.2420 g.
0.4575	0.2425	0.2429
0.4585	0.2430	0.2411

Analysis of a sample of Bauxite from the Central Provinces of India.—1.0 G. of the sample was taken for analysis.

TABLE V.

Wt. of phosphate-precipitate.	Wt. of TiO ₂ from phosphate.	TiO ₂ determined by Oxide-method.
0.2951 g.	0.1564 g.	0.1580 g.
0.2950	0.1564	0.1584

From the above experiments it is conclusively proved that titanium can be determined quantitatively as phosphate.

These precipitates of phosphates did not give variable results even when fused over and over again to get constant values and the operation repeated.

This method has the advantage that Ti is separated from Fe and almost all other metals except Zr, in a form that may be easily filtered and washed and is serviceable for the determination of small quantity of Ti, in presence of Fe. [This method is inapplicable in presence of thorium also.]